

EFFECTS OF RESIN IMPREGNATION RATES ON PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF BALANCE PAPERS

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Abstract

The polymerization of a resin in a décor paper during the pressing results in a tension. This tension may deform a board. The problem is solved by a treated paper, which is laid under the board, the balance paper. The tensions are balanced and the board stays even.

This study is aimed to determine effects of resin rate on physical properties of balance paper. Non-impregnated balance paper, with grammages of 70 g/m², was supplied a commercial company. The balance papers were impregnated with resin (urea (50%) and melamine (50%) formaldehyde) in five different rates, namely 125, 150, 175, 200, and 225%. Then, breaking length, burst and tear indices, air permeability, water absorptiveness (COBB), density and bulk of each balance paper were determined and compared with each other.

As a result, the air permeability, density and Cobb values of the impregnated balance papers were significantly improved when compared to non-impregnated papers. Besides, the breaking length and burst and tear indices were decreased by using resin. The balance papers impregnated with 125% resin gave the best results in the breaking length and tear and burst indices. As resin impregnation rates increases, air permeability, Cobb and density of the balance papers had decreased.

Keywords: Balance paper, resin, physical properties

REÇİNE EMDİRME ORANLARININ BALANS KAĞITLARININ FİZİKSEL ÖZELLİKLERİ ÜZERİNE ETKİLERİ

Özet

Reçine emdirilmiş dekor kağıtları levha üzerine preslenirken ortaya bir gerilim kuvveti çıkmaktadır. Meydana gelen bu gerilmeler levhaya hasar verebilir. Bu problem levhanın alt kısmına preslenen işlem görmüş balans kağıtları ile çözülmektedir. Gerilmeler balans kağıtları sayesinde dengelenir ve levhanın çarpılmasını engeller.

Bu çalışma balans kağıtlarına uygulanan reçine miktarının bu kağıtların fiziksel özellikleri üzerine etkilerini belirlemeyi amaçlamıştır. 70 gramajında işlem görmemiş ham balans kağıtları ticari bir firmadan temin edilmiş ve bu çalışmada kullanılmıştır. Balans kağıtlarına %125, 150, 175, 200, 225 oranlarında reçine (%50 Üre Formaldehit + %50 Melamin Formaldehit) emdirilmiştir. Her bir balans kağıdının kopma uzunluğu, patlama ve yırtılma indisleri, hava geçirgenliği, su emiciliği (Cobb), yoğunluk ve hacimlilik özellikleri belirlenmiştir.

Sonuç olarak, reçine emdirilmemiş kağıtlar ile karşılaştırıldığında, reçine emdirilmiş kağıtların hava geçirgenliği, Cobb ve yoğunlukları belirgin bir şekilde iyileşmiştir. Bunun yanı sıra, reçine kullanımı ile balans kağıtların kopma uzunluğu, patlama ve yırtılma indislerinde düşüşler meydana gelmiştir. Kopma uzunluğu, patlama ve yırtılma indislerinde en iyi sonuçları %125 reçine emdirilmiş balans kağıtları vermiştir. Emdirilen reçine oranındaki arttıkça balans kağıtlarının kopma uzunluğu, patlama ve yırtılma indisi azalmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Balans kağıtları, reçine, fiziksel özellikler

1 Introduction

Particleboard and fiberboard panel products are coated by impregnated papers, paint, print, varnish, veneers, laminates, foils, etc. Lamination is a process that imparts a pleasing appearance in addition to improving the physical, mechanical, and optical properties. The layers of a laminate floor are illustrated in Fig. 1. The main surface characteristics obtained by the lamination process are resistance to scratching, abrasion, moisture, heat, and to some household chemicals. The purposes of these applications are to increase physical, mechanical, and surface properties, to suppress the absorption of water and humidity, and to eliminate the release of formaldehyde emission [1]-[4]. In addition, the resin type used in the production of substrate and coating materials affects the final product's properties. As a rule, urea and melamine

formaldehyde resins (synthetic resins) are extensively used as binder adhesives in the production of panel and coating materials [5].

Figure 40. Layers of a laminated floor

Balance paper (stabilizing layer) is laminated onto the base or back of modular furniture and laminate floorings to protect the product from moisture damage and keep it from changing its

shape (Fig. 1.). It protects the products from moisture and distortion and allows the product to remain stable. Balance papers are used as a surface covering material in conjunction with high pressure decorative laminate and a substrate such as particleboard to balance the assembly. They must be impregnated with special synthetic resin before applying to the products. The resin penetration is relatively high, generally between 120-200% depending on paper weight [6].

Balance paper balances out the pressure on the substrate caused by the expansion and contraction of wood cells. When a paper is bonded to both sides of the panel, each side is equally expanding and contracting and thus the panel is "balanced" - the stress of the wood cell movement is equal on both sides of the panel. This prevents warping while the veneer adhesive is curing and prevents warping caused by seasonal humidity changes in the weeks, months, and years after the project is finished.

For impregnating, papers must have a high moisture resistance and the right porosity to accept the proper amount of resin. It must also be possible to impregnate the paper with the appropriate synthetic resins that can include urea formaldehyde, melamine formaldehyde, acrylic, phenolic resins, and mixtures thereof. The coating is laminated under high pressure and heat with particleboards or other substrates [7].

In this study, it was aimed to determine the effects of resin impregnation rates on the physical properties of the balance papers.

2 Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University Faculty of Forestry, Pulp and Paper Production Laboratory. Balance papers with grammages of 70 (g/m²) and resins were taken from a commercial suppliers in Turkey. The papers were impregnated by using urea formaldehyde (UF) and melamine formaldehyde (MF).

2.1 Resin Impregnation

The balance papers were impregnated with 50% UF and 50% MF. The resin was applied to the papers in certain rates (125%, 150%, 175%, 200%, and 250%). The impregnation was applied by using a roller brush and impregnated papers were dried overnight at room temperature.

2.2 Determining of Physical Properties of Balance Papers

The dried papers were conditioned at 23±1 °C and 65% relative humidity in conditioning room accordance with TAPPI T 402 om-88 standard. Then, the conditioned papers were prepared for physical tests.

The breaking length (TAPPI T494 om-01 (2006)), burst index (TAPPI T403 om-97 (1997)), tear index (TAPPI T414 om-12 (2012)), air permeability (TAPPI T460 om-02 (2006)), bulk and density (TAPPI T220 sp-10 (2010)), and water absorptiveness (TAPPI T441 om-09 (2013)) [8]. The tests were carried out in triplicate.

3 Results and Discussions

The physical properties of impregnated balance papers were presented in Table 1 in order to compare with each other.

Table 14. The physical properties of the balance papers

Resin rates (%)	Length		Index		Air Permeability (m ³ /min)	Bulk (cm ³ /g)	Density (g/cm ³)	Cobb (g/m ²)
	Breaking (km)	Burst (kPa•m ² /g)	Tear (mN•m ² /g)	Index				
0	2.06	1.17	3.92	501	1.83	0.55	102	
125	2.07	1.76	0.81	109	1.37	0.73	22	
150	1.37	1.27	1.31	43	1.00	1.00	17	
175	1.36	0.79	1.35	37	1.10	0.91	9	
200	1.32	0.48	1.37	32	1.03	0.97	7	
225	0.92	0.49	1.05	27	1.04	0.96	9	

Breaking length is generally used in the paper trade to characterize the inherent strength of paper. It affords an excellent basis for comparing the strength of papers made from different furnishes and having different basis weight. The breaking length of the papers impregnated with 125% resin was found to be similar with the non-impregnated balance papers. When Table 1 analyzed, as resin impregnation rates increases, the breaking length had decreased. Bursting strength tells how much pressure paper can tolerate before rupture. According to Table 1, papers impregnated with 125% resin gave the best result in burst index (1.76 kPa•m²/g). Increases of resin rates have a negative effect on burst strength. Tearing resistance indicates the behavior of paper in various end use situations; such as evaluating web runnability, controlling the quality of newsprint and characterizing the toughness of packaging papers where the ability to absorb shocks is essential. With resin impregnation, tear indices of the balance papers were significantly decreased from 3.92 to 0.81 (mN•m²/g). As can be seen in Fig. 2, the breaking length and tear and burst indices of the balance papers were decreased by applying resin impregnation.

Figure 41. Effects of resin rates on the breaking lengths and burst and tear indices of the balance papers

Increases of the paper grammages by using resin decreased the fiber rate in paper. Therefore, decreases of the breaking length and burst and tear indices have occurred [9].

Figure 42. Effects of resin rates on the Cobb and air permeability of the balance papers

The air permeability and Cobb values of the impregnated papers were decreased when compared with non-impregnated papers (Fig. 3). Resin usage increases the resistance of paper against water and air [10]. Cobb has an important role for balance papers due to usage area. The boards used in outdoors are required to be water resistant. Therefore, the Cobb values of the balance papers must be lower. With resin impregnation, the Cobb value of the balance paper was decreased from 102 to 7 g/m². The air permeability of the balances papers were also decreased by using resin from 501 to 27 (m³/min). Air resistance is measured as the time for a given volume of air to flow through a specimen under specified conditions. Balance papers prevent the formation of nutrient media for pests such as insects, thereby preventing damage to the fiberboards and particle boards.

High density causes more compact and tighter structure. Papers of high density consist of more resin and woody cells than papers of low density. For this reason, high density improves the properties of products such as fiberboards and particle boards [11], [12]. The density of the balance papers were increased from 0.55 to 1.0 g/cm³ by applying resin impregnation. Attendantly, the bulk of the balance papers were decreased (Fig. 4).

Figure 43. Effects of resin rates on the bulk and density of the balance papers

4 Conclusion

5. 125% resin impregnation were improved the physical properties of the balance papers. Especially air permeability, Cobb value, and density of the balance papers were improved about 78.2%, 89.1%, and 24.7%, respectively.
6. The physical properties of the balance papers such as breaking length and burst and tear indices were decreased by using resin which increases fragility of papers.
7. Due to higher Cobb and air permeability, 225% resin impregnated balance papers were suitable for fiberboards and particle boards used in outdoor applications such as wall coverings.
8. When the balance papers impregnated with different resin rates compared with each other, using 125% resin is better for fiberboards and particle boards used in indoor applications such as ceiling, flooring, and furnitures.

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